

NOTES

Stoichiometric experiment has indicated the absorption of 1.5 moles of V(v) per mole of the ketones. Product analysis has been conducted at kinetic conditions. Naphthoic acids (α and β), 3-acetyl 1-naphthol (m.p. 170° lit. m.p.⁵ 173°-74°) and 4-acetyl 1-naphthol (m.p. 196°. Lit. m.p.⁵ 198°) have been isolated from the ketones. These phenols exhibited their characteristic tests.

The oxidation of acetonephthones with V(v) has been studied in acetic acid water medium. The reaction has been found to obey second order kinetics. Increase in the proportion of acetic acid in the reaction mixtures increases the rate of oxidation in a non-linear fashion. The reaction, therefore, appears to take place either between a non-polar molecule and an ion or between two ions in accordance to the Brönsted-Christinsen-Scatchard equation⁶.

It is observed that the rate of oxidation of acetyl naphthalenes is faster than acetophenone under similar conditions⁴. This is perhaps due to the oxidation of the naphthalene ring itself in addition

contrast to the observation of Rout *et al.*⁷ for the Ce(IV) oxidation of these ketones. It has been explained that the decrease in rate constant of 1-acetyl naphthalene is due to the steric interference of the H atom at position 8 with the approach of the oxidant. If V(v) does not suffer from this steric effect than the ratio of ionic radii of these ions should correspond to the ratio of the rate constants. The ratio of the ionic radii is 1.5 and the ratio of rate constant is 1.7, which is a good agreement.

TABLE 1

Temperature = 40°
HAC : H₂O = 50 : 50 (v/v)
 $\beta K = \beta$ -Acetonephthone

10 ³ [βK]	10 ³ [V(v)]	[H ₂ SO ₄]	10 ² k in M ⁻¹ min ⁻¹
20.0	5.0	3.0	6.4
20.0	10.0	3.0	6.0
20.0	16.7	3.0	7.2
15.0	10.0	3.0	6.48
25.0	10.0	3.0	6.34
40.0	10.0	3.0	6.55
50.0	10.0	3.0	6.67
50.0	20.0	2.5	2.20
50.0	20.0	3.00	6.75
50.0	20.0	3.50	8.77
50.0	20.0	3.60	9.76
50.0	20.0	3.75	13.96
50.0	20.0	4.00	20.30

TABLE 2

Dependence of rate on solvent composition.

Temperature = 40°
10³[βK] = 25.0M.
10³[V(v)] = 10.0M
[H₂SO₄] = 4.0M

% HAC	10 ² k in M ⁻¹ min ⁻¹
37.5	10.45
45.0	13.5
50.0	20.1
62.5	87.05
75.0	522.00

TABLE 3

Dependence of rate on [βK] in HClO₄

Temperature = 40°
[HClO₄] = 3.0M
[V(v)] = 0.01M.

10 ² [βK]	10 ² k in M ⁻¹ min ⁻¹
100.0	15.95
75.0	17.00
60.0	18.12
50.0	18.71

TABLE 4

$\alpha K = \alpha$ -Acetonephthone
Dependence of rate on [αK] at
[H₂SO₄] = 2.2M,
[V(v)] = 0.01M and
Temperature = 40°.

10 ² [αK]	10 ² k in M ⁻¹ min ⁻¹
50.0	3.92
60.0	3.82
75.0	3.70

TABLE 5

Dependence of rate on cationic species at [βK] = 0.1M,
[H₂SO₄] = 2.2M, Temperature = 40°.

Oxidant	Concentration in M	10 ² k in M ⁻¹ min ⁻¹
V ₂ O ₅	0.0196	3.58
Na ₃ VO ₄	0.0157	3.07

TABLE 6

Rate dependence on temperature, values of Arrhenius parameters and absolute theory.

10³[Ketone] = 75.0, 10³[V(v)] = 10.0, [H₂SO₄] = 2.2M,
HAC = 37.5%

Ketone	10 ² k in M ⁻¹ min ⁻¹				E in K.cals mole ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger in e.u.	ΔF^\ddagger in K.cals/mole
	35°	40°	45°	50°			
αK	1.00	1.47	2.62	4.12	19.12	-14.4	23.7
βK	0.464	0.75	1.62	3.57	31.32	+31.1	21.4

to the oxidation of the -COCH₃ group. The order of reactivity of acetyl naphthalene is 1-acetyl naphthalene > 2-acetyl naphthalene, which is in

The oxidation has also been studied at various temperatures. The values of energy and entropy of activation have been determined.

The formation of naphthols suggests the attack of the oxidant at the free double bond of acetyl naphthalene. It is known that V(v) attacks naphthalene and other polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons⁸, provided that acetic acid is present as a co-solvent. Since the reaction is done always at lower [V(v)], the naphthol thus produced does not get further oxidised. Ce(IV) oxidation of naphthalene also produces α -naphthol⁹. So, the different stages for the oxidation can be represented as given in Scheme-1.

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